

The Faustus-Figure of Christopher Marlowe and Thomas Mann: A Study in the Birth and Death of Anthropocentric Humanism

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<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 20, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Faustus-figure, Thomas Mann, Anthropocentric Humanism, Nihilism</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5586317</p>	<p><i>Over the past four centuries nearly two hundred writers have felt inspired to use the Faustus-legend to express the striving of their time for the unknowable, the unattainable and the impermissible. This study examines two Faustus-figures, one of the earliest great creations, Christopher Marlowe's Doctor Faustus, and one of the latest significant versions, Thomas Mann's Adrian Leverkuehn. It concentrates on the use which both writers made of the literary Faustus-tradition in order to illuminate certain aspects of their so widely varying reality, namely, Elizabethan England and Twentieth century Germany. It then discusses the link between the two Faustus- versions. Marlowe gives through his Faustus-figure a warning that the anthropocentric concept of freedom cannot lead to the fulfillment of man's aspirations because it is fraught with danger. Mann demonstrates 350 years later, the truth of Marlowe's fears in the fate of this Faustus-figure, whose reality is sterility, nihilism and atheism. Thus the literary Faustus-tradition, used to portray the climax and collapse, the birth and death of anthropocentric humanism in the twentieth century, completes a full cycle. This work aims at finding the link which connects these two artistic versions of such widely differing realities. It is a comparative study only in the sense that it analyses two different versions of the same literary figure, confronts each with the realistic background against which it was created and draws certain conclusions about the author's implied evaluations and comments. Apart from this, no other element of comparison enters the work.</i></p>

Introduction

Since its beginning in the sixteenth century the Faustus-legend has attracted numerous writers, readers and audiences up to the present day. There are 166 literary treatments of the theme, 9 ballads, 17 puppet-plays. 12 popular pieces, 7 chapbooks, and many more versions are known to have been lost. These figures make one wonder about the roots of the irresistible enchantment with this legend. What made the historical Faustus such a fundamentally symbolic figure? Bernard Levin tries to explain the extraordinary fascination with the Faustus-figure when he says:

"To discover the unknowable, to achieve the unattainable, dare the impermissible- these are the strivings that have made the human race what it is, and throughout all history there have been those who thought evolution too slow, wished to circumvent its deliberate rituals, and were willing to seek supernatural aid to enable them to do so."

In terms of sixteenth century life the unknowable, the unattainable, impermissible and the supernatural were concrete factors which the individual had to face; but are these concepts still of major significance for modern man? Did not science supply the answer to most mysteries, technical achievement attain even man's journey to the planets, and moral freedom lift the taboos of the impermissible? Can twentieth century still believe in the supernatural? If the reality of man's life has changed so radically within 350 years, how can a literary tradition, which basically deals with man's rebellion against imposed outer concerns, which differs so widely?

These questions have given the impetus to this study. They have directed the attention to one of the earliest great Faustus-versions, the play the Tragical History of the Life and Death of Doctor Faustus, by Christopher Marlowe and the novel, Doctor Faustus: The life of German Composer Adrian Leverkuehn as Told by a Friend, by Thomas Mann.

The English dramatist Christopher Marlowe (1564-1593) lived in an era when Renaissance ideals freed the human mind from the taboos imposed by medieval doctrine, when inherited concepts were discarded in order to form new theories and when changes confronted the individual on every level.

Thomas Mann (1875-1955), one of the most representative of twentieth century German writers, witnessed the changes in his country that were brought about by the emergence of a totalitarian state which finally forced him to exile, to witness his nation collapse as a helpless spectator. Both artists, so far apart in time, space and the reality of their lives, have used the Faustus-figure to express the struggle of the individual against imposed limitations; against boundaries set for man in his human capabilities and against cultural norms, imposed by society.

The study intends to show that Marlowe used the Faustus-figure to symbolize a new tendency which emerged in the Elizabethan age, which was the trend towards anthropocentric humanism; and that Mann, 350 years later, through his own Faustus-figure portrayed the climax and collapse of an anthropocentric world in the twentieth century.

1. The Historical Faustus

The fact that Faustus, an actual historical person, exists in Germany in the 16th century is proved by documentary evidence. His name is generally stated as Georg Faustus or Jeorg Faustus; and only Philipp Melanchthon, the 16th century theologian and educator, speaks of him as Johann Faust, probably confusing the name with that of the Heidelberg student Johann Faust ex Symmern.

The testimony dealing with Faustus's life takes three forms; firstly, there are three official sources: According to Hans Muller Cammermeister's annual accounting Faust, Doctor of philosophy, received on February 12, 1520, ten gulden for a horoscope from the Bishop of Bamberg. According to the Protocol Council and the Registry of banishment Doctor Jeorg Faustus of Heidelberg was exiled from the town of Ingolstadt in 1523. The cause was not mentioned. According to the Town Council Ruling of Nuernberg. Dated June 10, 1532 an application made by Faustus for residency Nuernberg vicinity was rejected. This document describes Faustus as "the great Sodomite and Nigromant" which indicates reasons for the refusal.

In these three sources Faustus appears as an astrologer and magician who tries to influence ordinary people in his favor but is already in conflict with the authorities. Secondly, there are several personal documentary reports: the most important testimonials are those of Melanchthon, entitled *Locorum Communiu Colletae*, dated Basel, 1563, of Trithemius, the abbot of Sponheim, named *Epistolae Familiares* dated Hagenau, 1536, because they describe personal encounters and give actual details of Faustus' speeches and actions. Other persons who provide valid information in their writings about Faustus' life are: the humanist scholar Conradus Mutianus; the Prior of Rebdorf, Kilian Leib; Doctor Johannes Wierus; Philip von Hutten; and Joachim Camerarius. These testimonials provide a certain amount of biographical data. Thirdly, there are a number of printed sources which are likely to date from Faustus' lifetime and merely report his practices, such: Luther's tabletalks from the Thirties; Begrardi's tale printed in the *Index sanitatis*.

A comprehensive summary of all above sources establishes the following historical facts with regard to Faustus' life; Sojourn in the Gelnhausen in 1506, in Kreuznach in 1507; visit in Erfurt in 1513; in Bamberg 1520, exile from Ingolstadt in 1528; stay in Nuernberg in 1532. It also assures the following dates as reasonably certain: birth 1480 in Knittlingen, first stay in Wuerzburg 1506; flight from Wittenberg 1525/1532; return to Nuernberg and Wuerzburg 1534-1536; thereafter retirement; death in 1540 or 1541 in Staufen Breisgau. It is probable that Faustus visited other European capitals and centers of learning as reported in various other and later writings, but as these mingle fact and fiction they cannot be recognized as evidence. No portrait of Faustus exists.

Considering the social, political and religious conditions that existed in Germany in the 16th century, a fuller picture of Faustus' life emerges. Nothing definite is known about Faustus social background but judging by the rustic character of the tiny country-town of Knittlingen, the assumption is reasonable that he was born in to a peasant family. Apparently he attended the school of Latin that existed in Knittlingen already at that time. Later he joined a group of travelling journeymen who entertained people with performances and tales of strange happenings desperate social conditions of the peasantry at the time may have occasioned this. He was probably brought up in the catholic doctrine, which was the only one in those parts but he must have come into contact with Protestantism when he later travelled to Wittenberg. Judging by Trithemius' account, Faustus didn't feel bound to either denomination and stated that he was rationalist. Both, the catholic abbot, and the protestant Melanchthon, brought about Faustus contemptuously and accused him of preaching against the Church, which explains their hostile attitude.

Apparently Faustus acquired uncommon degree of knowledge, especially in natural sciences and medicine. He never attended a university. A certain Johannes Faustus ex Symmern did pass the degree of baccalaureate in 1509 at the University of Heidelberg, but closer examination reveals that this is a different person as no other university record the attendance of Georg Faustus, it is believed that he simply assumes the titles of magister and doctor of philosophy. However Faustus didn't have close contact with university circles and made use of his suggestive-hypnotic powers in order to impress them. He is known to have explained natural phenomena still unknown at his time. But the fact he assumed bombastic titles- such as "Magister Georg sabellicus Faust the younger, fountain of Necromancy, astrologer, second of the Magicians, Palmist, Pyromant, Aeromant, Second in Hydromancy" brought him the scorn of the scholars of his time who accused him of dealing in black magic. Faustus greatly impressed simple folk. He claimed that he knew by heart the complete works of Plato and Aristotle, that he could perform miracles as Christ did, that he was the greatest alchemist of all times and could achieve anything he desired. His reputation as a astrologer and magician spread and brought him into contact with upper classes and aristocracy. He did not settle anywhere permanently but led a life of constant change and adventure for about thirty years. Occasionally he was given a respectable post, like that of schoolmaster in Kreuznach, but he was soon forced to flee when it was discovered he encourages sodomy. There are other instances of official threats of punishment, such as the order for his arrest by Elector of Saxony when Faustus stayed in Wittenberg or that of exile from Ingolstadt and the refusal for residency from Nuernberg. That Faustus died of unnatural death is stressed in both accounts of event. Nowadays it is believed that chemical experiments, maybe an explosion was the cause of death, but both chroniclers attribute the death to the evil spirit who choked him.

The picture that emerges of the historical Faustus is not a favorable one. It should, however, be kept in mind that all events of his life have been described by people in authority who were obviously hostile towards Faustus and his influence on the common people. It should be forgotten that Germany in the first half of the 16th century was in a state of social unrest, where feudalism was crumbling, the aristocracy threatened and the peasantry in a state of revolt. There is no doubt about Faustus' close relationship with simple folk. It is likely that they saw in him a man who had burst the bonds of medieval restrictions and risen above the misery of his time. This picture of Faustus emerges mainly from the oral tradition of the common folk where, in the course of time, his powers as a magician were more and more emphasized.

3. Comparison of the two Faustus-figures

The differences and similarities of the world in which the two Faustus-figures live, of the conflict that confronts them, of the consequences the choice of their action and the final outcome of their fate. Marlowe's Faustus was born into a world where medieval systems were falling into ruin and Elizabethan concepts were growing underfoot. Changes were confronting the individual on every level, giving him more freedom but also more responsibilities. This development inevitably brought about a certain confusion and insecurity. After the acceptance of the Copernican and Keplerian-cosmical theories the medieval world-picture diablo-centric earth was no longer tenable. The inherited system of social order based on the concept of the Great Chain of Being and the System of correspondences could no longer be applied to the changed material reality which confronted members of all social classes. The parochial hierarchy of the church, which had dominated the spiritual world of man, was destroyed through the reformation and contemplative scholasticism was no longer through of as the only means to knowledge. The new cosmological world picture freed man from his sublunary degraded state. He learned that social systems could be over turned and his quest for success, action, power, fame and glory was to be no longer restrained. The search for knowledge was to help him to dominate the world by active pursuit of natural sciences directed towards the practical utilitarian. His desire for religious enquiry was to be no longer restricted. He used all his faculties to determine the truth and to stand "face to face" with God. The medieval dictum that "this was the best of all possible worlds" was to be taken at face value.

Marlowe's Faustus, the accomplished scholar, so richly endowed with "learning's golden gifts" was placed into the center of this world. Three hundred-fifty years later another Faustus was born. What kind of Mann's Faustus-figure find? It was a world greatest scientific and materialistic achievement. Man had accumulated so much technical knowledge that he could force the earth to yield sufficient nutrition for all humanity and to give up its treasures for his pleasure and comfort. He could combat many diseases, foretell many natural disasters; cosmology was no longer mystery, man had conquered the sky and the flight to the stars was just around the corner. Yet, this world, so full of positive, materialistic achievement was not considered by its inhabitants "the best of all possible worlds". There was a deep feeling of this dissatisfaction. All social classes were struggling either to receive a larger share of the new wealth or to maintain the privilege that this wealth had brought them. In this struggle all inherited principles of value were discarded and the ruthlessness of power struggle prevailed. Irrationality and chaos seemed to rule this world which its philosophers tried to explain through the domination of blind, primordial Will. They were either convinced that material progress would never solve man's misery, only acceptance and suffering could do so, or they advocated destruction to the point of nihilism were only the fittest could survive. In spiritual sphere man was in the process of the dethroning God and setting up himself as an object of reverence. Only in art a remnant of an inherited world could be found in the harmony and beauty of bygone age. But this harmony was false and it clashed with the pessimism of true reality. This was the world into which Mann's Faustus, the artist, so richly endowed with genius was born.

Thus Marlowe's Faustus commands a world of optimism, enthusiasm and desire for material wealth while Mann's Faustus inherits a world of pessimism, nihilism, satiation with materialistic achievement.

4. The Conflict

Faustus the 16th century scholar was facing a dilemma. The learning he had acquired was motivated by the medieval outlook which was other worldly. It considered this life only as transitory stage in the journey to true happiness. This philosophy taught that ambition was sinful, acquiescence and acceptance holy. How could Faustus convert this learning into a guiding principle of life in a world that was so totally opposed in its reality to the aims of this teaching? Faustus realized that orthodox study, totally directed towards the harmony in the microcosm, could not give him a deeper and more satisfying insight into life fully absorbed with the acquisition of power in the microcosm. Traditional learning had to be discarded; yet, it was not easy for a scholar dismiss a system which had become part of his existence. He felt a need for justification and did so by attributing lowly and materialistic motives to the various branches of learning. These Faustus claimed, demeaned his own aspirations which appeared to him as ennobling endeavors to widen man's horizon. With the Elizabethan call to action man had the freedom to decide for himself how far was going to be the architect of his own fortune. The primary aim in life became public accomplishment and Faustus, the scholar intoxicated with the desire for "a world of profit and delight" where he could demi-god, was ready to use black magic, forbidden science, to help him achieve his aims. The loss of the salvation of his soul was no sacrifice to him because in the new era of enlightenment such beliefs were "old wives tales". The devil, the agent of forbidden science, did not confirm Faustus new doctrine. He embodied the medieval world-picture which, after all, had created him. As the representative of an evil outside order he assured Faustus that any existence without God meant

living in hell. Faustus however, remained definite in his new doctrine. If he could create a temporary paradise on earth- and he believed that knowledge and power could do so- then salvation would become superfluous. The twentieth century Faustus faced not so much a conflict as an impasse in his irrational and chaotic world. He suffered from a feeling of void and emptiness his genius could not overcome the sterility which paralyzed all inspiration. As an artist, he despised the false representation of life which his contemporaries produced. He longed to tear the false mask of the face of art, but his genius alone could not supply the means. Art should be passionate transfiguration of true reality and the reality of twentieth century was devoid of human feelings. In Faustus' materialistic and anthropocentric world "human love that warmth" appeared as the most desirable quality, the only divine element in the world without God. Faustus was aware that his intellectual genius alienated him from human warmth and that it drove him into a superior isolation. Only primitive, instinctive forces could conquer intellect and Faustus encouraged these, even at the risk of physical and mental ruin, because they filled the unbearable void. The contract with the devil meant to the twentieth century Faustus only a confirmation of a general development which could be discerned indirectly since his childhood and had started directly with the deliberate infection with disease. The devil, as hallucinatory experience, was fully a part of Faustus' own identity. He promised Faustus highest artistic achievement at the price of 'human love that warmth'. This offer contained a chance and challenge for Faustus. Human warmth was denied to him already and he was aware that his existence was, actually, hell on earth, but through true artistic creation he might gain the possibility of a breakthrough to the world.

Thus Marlowe's Faustus who inherited a world-order, in which he was part of a great divine system, rebelled against the confines which this system imposed. In order to break free he sold himself to the evil order. He was convinced that with the temporary freedom and power which the evil order promised him, he could establish an independent human order and create paradise on earth. Though he was warned that once he left his place in the divine order he would be living in hell, Faustus' dream of human paradise conquered all doubts.

In the world-order into which Mann's Faustus was born, the divine elements were missing and it created an unbearable void. The evil order promised release from this emptiness through its own dark force. It had directed Faustus's life since childhood and Faustus did not hesitate to sign the pact because, basically it did not change his situation. The 'hell on earth' which the devil imposed upon him, was only an intensification of his actual condition, of which Faustus was fully aware. In the promised power of artistic creativity Faustus saw his only chance of gaining his artistic soul which might enable his breakthrough to the world.

5. The Result of the Pact with the Devil

For the 16th century Faustus the pact with the devil was the turning point of his life. As long as he had been part of the divine order his ultimate aspirations had tended towards the spiritual, though he emphasized the physical means. The Elizabethan call to fame and glory was based on a concept of combining Christian chivalry with that of classical nobility. The advances of natural sciences were encouraged to confirm inherited principles, not overthrow them. It shows that religion still directed science when it recommended the conquest of external nature of for the benefit of man who should simultaneously study his inner world to conquer his weakness. But once Marlowe's Faustus became part of evil order, all his positives aspirations turned into negative desire. His twenty-four years of freedom and power were a continuous downward movement; the benefits of the pack were illusions: travelling among the stars only taught him the utter insignificance of man in the vastness of the cosmical order; in his hope of gaining superhuman knowledge from the magical books he was deceived, natural sciences provided only information, they did not solve mysteries of existence; hi physical desires for power, wealth and pleasure, though appeased by apparent satiation, did not bring him happiness; instead of becoming the world liberator, he became the entertainer of mankind; and his dream of earthly paradise turned into the reality of hell on earth.

Apart from physical deterioration, the development after the pact of Mann's Faustus differs radically from that of Marlowe's. Having been raised under the influence of evil order, Faustus recognized the powers promised by the devil in their true light. It was the means to emerge from the impasse and to establish a new system to express the reality of twentieth century. Faustus created his truly nihilistic version of the world, in which he tore the false mask of the face of reality.

But after establishing his truly demonic world- picture, Faustus came for the first time face to face with innocence to which he responded automatically with human warmth, a quality which he had thought absent in himself. But human warmth was the price he had promised the devil for the acquisition of his creative powers and thus innocence had to be destroyed. This event revealed to Faustus the error of his ways. Instead of trying to fill the void by searching for innocence- which alone leads to human love- he substituted the intoxication with the dark forces of instinct which destroyed innocence. Thus Faustus had become guilty. This revelation was the turning point for the 20th century Faustus. He broke with evil order no longer was his art a nihilistic statement of a satanic synthesis was replaced by unhappy truth of 20th century reality, where man bewails the loss of innocence.

The spiral downward movement from positive to the negative of the development of Marlowe's Faustus after signing the pact with the devil takes a different course in Mann's Faustus. Here the descending line reaches its deepest point in the nihilistic world-picture but then takes an upward turn.

6. Faustus' End

The process of deterioration of Marlowe's Faustus was accompanied by a simultaneous increase of regret and a continuous wavering between hope and despair. Throughout his life Faustus had received continuous warnings from the divine order to mend his ways before it is too late. The outcome of the struggle between hope and despair is determined by the 16th century attitude towards religion which resulted from the reformation. Without the possibility of redemption from sin through the grace of God, Faustus who had willfully abandoned the divine order, could not return to it and had accept his reality as that of Calvinist reprobate. The evil order emerges as a victor in the struggle over human soul. The terrible end of Marlowe's Faustus is an example of the desperate state of mind of the sinner facing the Protestant image of God the Avenger. The recognition belong either to the divine or to the evil order, the only possible reality for the 16th century comes to Faustus too late for his own salvation.

The 20th century Faustus, though free from evil order, sees no possibility of reestablishing the divine order in his own reality, which remains a world without God. But Mann's Faustus does not despair. His hope is in the recognition of evil as the first step towards the struggle against it. If man fights the evil order which deprived him of human warmth, then he will increase the divine element in his nature and make a new world in which innocence and survive. The complete mental and physical collapse of Mann's Faustus was a necessity for the birth of a glimmer of hope for the future.

In their final recognition and acceptance both, Marlowe's and Mann's Faustus-figures, achieve greatness, but while the 16th century Faustus is doomed, the 20th century Faustus sees a faraway hope in a new beginning.

7. The Birth and Death of Anthropocentric Humanism

The outcome of this final analysis leads to the link between the two Faustus-figures. Marlowe's Faustus pleading "in tears and revolt for rehabilitation", embodies the birth of anthropocentric humanism, generated by the Renaissance and the reformation. It has further been pointed that Marlowe did not believe that anthropocentric concept of freedom would lead to the fulfillment of man's aspirations and that its pursuit was fraught with dangers.

Later 350 years, Mann demonstrated the fate of another Faustus-figure the truth of Marlowe's fears in the terrible reality of totality anthropocentric world where Faustus is dominated by artistic sterility, national fanaticism, intellectual nihilism and the void of spiritual atheism, which combine to lead to his destruction. Mann shows that the life-span of anthropocentric humanism, which began when Augustine's summary of the Christian ideal of humanism, of theocentric humanism, "love God and do as you please!", was foreshortened into "Do as you please!", has now run its full cycle and must come to an end.

8. The Question of this Study

If the reality of man's life has changed so radically within 350 years, how can a literary tradition, which basically deals with man's rebellion against imposed limitations, be made the vehicle for the expression of human situation differing so widely? The answer is that the human situation of the 20th century, as presented by Mann, is the result of man's choice of action as described by Marlowe 350 years earlier.

The rebellion of the Renaissance-Faustus against medieval restricting concepts was legitimate one; the historical developments necessitated the adjustment, but the basic double-nature of man, which imposed the choice either following his physical or spiritual inclinations, had not changed. When Marlowe's Faustus joined the evil order, he freed the dark, primitive, instinctive forces in himself which converted his positive human aspirations into negative ones. Man, the creature, became the center of the macrocosm and anthropocentric humanism was born. The development of this trend was not fortuitous for man.

In the world of Mann's Faustus anthropological humanism reaches its climax: the dark forces rule the intellectual world in the form of pessimism and nihilism; the artistic world in the form of sterility; the social political world in the form of barbaric totalitarianism and the spiritual world in the form of atheism. However, as this principle is basically a negative one that converts all positive aspects of life to the negative, it's climax must constitute its end. Mann's Faustus finally achieves his breakthrough to humanity by rebelling against and abandoning anthropocentric humanism.

The choice of action, made 350 years earlier, has thus been reversed.

The fact that Marlowe's and Mann's Faustus-figures can be read as artistic visions of the birth and death of anthropocentric humanism adds a further possibility, a new dimension, to the appreciation of these two versions of the Faustus-legend as well as to the literary Faustus-tradition as a whole.

9. Conclusion

Pride is one of the Seven Deadly Sins, questionable the one that prompts all the others. Inside the Christian system, pride is a deadly inspiration since it causes the miscreant to fail to remember his fallen state. For Christians, men are fallen since birth, since they convey with them the pollutant of unique sin. A man made haughty with pride fails to remember that he shares Eve's wrongdoing, and should subsequently be saved by the endowment of effortlessness. Just God, through Christ, can administer this beauty, and the one who fails to remember that reality denies himself of the way to salvation. Hellfire is endless, however so is paradise. For a Christian, all that is important to be saved from

unceasing punishment is acknowledgment of Jesus Christ's elegance. Even in the wake of transferring ownership of his spirit to Satan, Faustus has the alternative of contrition that will save him from hellfire. Be that as it may, whenever he has subscribed to his own condemnation, Faustus appears to not be able to shift his direction. While Christianity appears to acknowledge even deathbed apology as worthy for the accomplishment of salvation, Marlowe toys with that concept, perhaps dismissing it for his own topical purposes.

The differences and similarities of the world in which the two Faustus-figures live, start from the conflict that confronts them, the consequences of their action and the final outcome of their fate. Marlowe's Faustus was born into a world where medieval systems were falling into ruin and Elizabethan concepts were growing underfoot. Changes were confronting the individual on every level, giving him more freedom but also more responsibilities. This development inevitably brought about a certain confusion and insecurity. He learned that social systems could be over turned and his quest for success, action, power, fame and glory was to be no longer restrained. The search for knowledge was to help him to dominate the world by active pursuit of natural sciences directed towards the practical utilitarian. His desire for religious enquiry was to be no longer restricted. He used all his faculties to determine the truth and to stand "face to face" with God.

Three hundred-fifty years later another Faustus was born. It was a world of greatest scientific and materialistic achievements. Man had accumulated so much technical knowledge that he could force the earth to yield sufficient nutrition for all humanity and to give up its treasures for his pleasure and comfort. He could combat many diseases, foretell many natural disasters; cosmology was no longer mystery, man had conquered the sky and the flight to the stars was just around the corner. Yet, this world, so full of positive, materialistic achievement was not considered by its inhabitants. There was a deep feeling of dissatisfaction. Irrationality and chaos seemed to rule this world which its philosophers tried to explain through the domination of blind. They were convinced that material progress would never solve man's misery, they advocated destruction to the point of nihilism were only the fittest could survive. In spiritual sphere man was in the process of the dethroning God and setting up himself as an object of reverence. Thus Marlowe's Faustus commands a world of optimism, enthusiasm and desire for material wealth while Mann's Faustus inherits a world of pessimism, nihilism and satiation with materialistic achievement.

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